

Characterization of Intra-Bandgap Defect States through Leakage Current Analysis for Optimization of 4H-SiC Photoconductive Switches

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Abstract

A method of characterizing mid-bandgap defect states in high purity semi-insulating 4H-SiC through leakage current analysis for optimization of SiC photoconductive switches is presented. The method utilizes two custom IV curve tracer systems to measure leakage currents through the material under various voltage/current conditions. The first system is used under low current conditions and is capable of measurements from 0 to 45 kV at currents ranging from 0 to 3 mA with pA resolution. A second system measures the transient discharge of a charged capacitor bank through the material. Due to power dissipation concerns, the second system is used for currents higher than 0.1 mA. Voltage/current measurements in this region (>0.1 mA) are of interest due to the information concerning defect states near the conduction band. These shallow defect states are detrimental to switching performance while offering little benefit to voltage hold-off. From the combined data of these two systems, characteristics of the defect states are extracted and presented. We further elucidate the effect of contact annealing temperature on shallow trap levels in electron-beam irradiated material (2×10^{18} $1/\text{cm}^2$).

1 INTRODUCTION

Any improvement in pulsed power technology depends largely on advances in reliable, high voltage and current switching. PCSSs are an alternative to other modern gas, solid-state, and mechanical switches by offering potentially low on-state resistance, high repetition rates (65 MHz), and open and close within nanoseconds with sub-nanosecond jitter. By using silicon carbide (SiC) instead of silicon (S), comparatively higher voltages can be switched due to a wider bandgap of 3.23 eV. The previous system used to gain current-voltage, IV, characteristics, a High Voltage Curve Tracer (HVTC) [1] developed in house, cannot be used at higher voltages. It produces a slow-ramping voltage across the device which works very well at low currents, but due to the non-linearity of PCSS resistance the power dissipation becomes too large at currents pushing beyond ~ 0.1 mA. This paper aims to characterize mid-bandgap defect states in SiC PCSSs by analyzing a pulsed current through the DUT in the off-state with a new test system via a capacitive transient discharge (TD) system instead of DC, through IV curves and transient decay. Previous work has been done on lateral switches,

however this work focuses on vertical switches [2, 3]. Switch specifications include a 6.35 mm x 6.35 mm x 450 μm SiC sample, 7.3 mm² circular contact area on the cathode and anode, and copper electrodes connected perpendicular to the contacts, as shown in Figure 1. Contacts are normal to the c-axis.

Figure 1. PCSS test geometry.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This system utilizes a 5 nF capacitor that is charged via a high voltage power supply and discharged across a PCSS, see Fig. 2. The voltage across a CVR is measured and the PCSS voltage is calculated in post-processing. When Relay 1 is closed and Relay 2 is open, the capacitor charges. Relay 1 is then opened to isolate the voltage source and Relay 2 closes to allow current to flow through the PCSS and CVR. The discrete equation used to calculate the voltage across the PCSS is given by equation (1).

$$V_{pcss_t} = V_{cap_{t-1}} - \frac{\int_{t-1}^t I_{CVR} d\tau}{C_{charging}} - \frac{C_{varistor} \int_{t-1}^t dV_{cvr}}{C_{charging}} - V_{cvr_t} \quad (1)$$

V_{pcss_t} is the voltage across the PCSS at time instance t , $V_{cap_{t-1}}$ is the voltage on the capacitor at the previous time instance, the current integral divided by capacitance, C , is the change in voltage from the previous time instant to the present instant, and V_{cvr_t} is the CVR voltage at time instance t .

Figure 2. Overall system circuit, minus the relay control circuitry.

PCSS off-state resistance is highly non-linear (decreases with increasing voltage). Multiple CVR values were used to for proper biasing at different charging voltages. Typical values range from 100 kΩ to 1 MΩ due to high PCSS resistance (50 MΩ - 20 GΩ). Clamping varistors are used for oscilloscope protection in case of switch breakdown. The overall system setup is shown in Fig. 3. A custom controller was also designed and built for testing automation, as can be seen in Figs. 3 and 4.

Figure 3. Experimental setup, including control board

Figure 4. Control board.

3 RESULTS

All three switches shown were tested until failure. Upon inspection, it is likely that in some of the species the breakdown path traveled along the surface around the PCSS slab through the cured epoxy rather than through the slab itself. If breakdown is through the device itself, space charge could be forming on the cathode and causing field enhancements, due to the materials low hole mobility ($< 120 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$). Also tested was the effect of contact annealing temperature on IV curve generation, both with the HVCT and TD systems. Increased anneal temperature decreases on-state resistance, and that effect was investigated here [2]. Each anneal was set for 3 minutes in an induction furnace filled with argon. Annealing also serves to remove unwanted trap levels in the band-gap, primarily leaving $Z_{1/2}$ and $\text{EH}_{6/7}$ trap levels [3]. These aid in higher blocking voltage, and the

removal of lower density traps improves on-state performance. Charged voltages were tested up to 20, 18.2, and 18 kV for the 900°C, 1,000°C, and 1,100°C anneals, respectively in DC, and up to 19.5, 18, and 17 kV on the TD system, respectively, see Figs. 5 and 6. Fig. 6 shows the highly non-linear aspect of PCSS resistance. Measurements below 0.01 mA are difficult due to the system noise floor. Current decay measurements were consistent among different shots for each PCSS. However, the 1,100°C anneal switch produced a lower current, see Fig. 6, than the other two switches, which is presently a topic of further investigation. Also being investigated is the difference between DC and pulsed IV curves. It is speculated that during the initial voltage rise time of the device, it takes time to initially fill each trap energy level which increases conduction. This is not an issue for the HVCT because it starts from low voltage, and has a slow ramp rate ($\sim 7 \text{ kV}/\text{min}$), so all trap levels would be filled before current measurement. For the 900°C and 1,000°C switches anneal temperature seems to be irrelevant as they both fall on the same discharge curve with the TD system.

Figure 5. Temporal recorded discharge from 19 kV for a vertical, 1,000°C contact annealed SiC switch.

Figure 6. IV curves of vertical switches using the High Voltage Curve Tracer (HVCT) and Transient Discharge (TD) setups. Currents do not surpass $\sim 0.1 \text{ mA}$ due to breakdown (likely in epoxy) at around 19 kV, but were able to surpass HVCT voltages.

7 CONCLUSION

In order to characterize the trap levels in 4H-SiC PCSSs, a setup was designed that enables applying a pulsed voltage across a PCSS in the off-state, and IV data is derived from the voltage vs. time data recorded by an oscilloscope. It is shown there are no additional shallow level traps within the voltage ranges tested. Simulation work is already underway to better understand transient behavior in non-illuminated PCSSs, which should provide an improved understanding of blocking characteristics and intra-band defects in 4H-SiC.

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